

GAPS IN THE COPYRIGHT AND DESIGN RIGHTS FOR NIGERIAN'S FASHION INDUSTRY

ABSTRACT

"If you want to be original, be ready to be copied." - Coco Chanel

The Global fashion industry is worth over \$2.5 trillion, with Africa's share estimated at less than 1% of that total. Meanwhile, Euromonitor suggests that the Sub-Saharan fashion market is worth \$31 billion, with Nigeria accounting for 15% of the \$31 billion (\$4.7 billion). Nigeria's fashion has arisen in size; it has grown 17% since 2010. The Nigerian fashion industry in recent years has guided itself into international recognition. With designs meeting the eyes of internationally recognized individuals and brands, it has proven itself to be an industry with commercial viability. Designers such as Deola Sagoe, Duro Olowu, Adebayo Oke Lawal and Amaka Osakwe, have put the Nigerian fashion industry in limelight, a light which seems to only get brighter. Events such as the Lagos Fashion Week with & Africa Fashion Week, started due to the exposure of brands that are based in Nigeria. The surge was possible because of the Runway Shows. Africa is rich due to their culture and tradition, especially when speaking of Fashion. The styles of dress provide a history of ancient cultures and ethnic backgrounds. Many ethnic cultures have a specific style that is sacred to their society and tribes. Despite having one of the largest apparel markets in the world, Nigeria is yet to extend intellectual property ("IP") rights to fashion design. Although there are several bills for the amendment of the Copyright Act, none of them can be said to really address the main issue affecting fashion designers and their rights; which is the availability of protection of the artistic work they create. Nigeria has no comprehensive and specific legal framework governing the fashion industry. Accordingly, specific legislation protecting fashion brands is non-existent. IP practitioners have therefore resorted to the general protection afforded under the existing legal framework for intellectual property in Nigeria. The existing legislation for this purpose includes; the Copyright Act, the Patents and Designs Act, and the Trademarks Act. Nonetheless, the application of these laws seems not to be sufficient and have been unsuccessful, and the vast majority of fashion design remains unprotected by IP law. A large number of designers, more than any other group of fashion designers, suffer the adverse effects of lack of IP rights for their designs. This paper analyzes the gaps in the existing copyright and design rights in the Nigeria Fashion Industry and the need for fashion design protection in Nigeria despite already existing IP rights.

CURRENT FRAMEWORK FOR PROTECTION OF THE FASHION INDUSTRY

Nigeria has no comprehensive and specific legal framework governing the fashion industry. IP practitioners have therefore resorted to the general protection afforded under the existing legal framework for intellectual property in Nigeria. The existing legislation for this purpose includes;

1. COPYRIGHT

Copyright is an area of IP law that grants some protection to fashion design. Copyright law provides protection for "original works of authorship fixed in any tangible medium of expression."¹ For a work to be considered original it must be "original to the author [and possess] at least some minimal degree of creativity. However, copyright limits its protection to works that are not meant to be reproduced, which in a sense, defeats the purpose of any fashion design"

Section 1 of the Nigerian Copyright Act provides for the types of works that are eligible for copyright and these are "*literary works, musical works, artistic works, cinematographic works, sound recording and broadcasts*".

However, Section 1(3) of Nigeria's Copyright Act states:

"An artistic work shall not be eligible for copyright, if at the time when the work is made, it is intended by the author to be used as a model or pattern to be multiplied by any industrial process."

This means that a designer's sketches are only protected by copyright as long as they fulfill the requirement of originality and there is no intention for it to be reproduced. As a result, protection under the Nigerian Copyright Act is not available where a designer intends to mass produce his or her garments thereby engaging in Industrial Application. Copyright limits its protection to works that are not meant to be reproduced, which in a sense, defeats the purpose of any fashion design. This is a disadvantage to Nigerian designers because commercially marketed designs are unprotected under the Copyright Act.²

¹ Section 2 of the Copyright Act Chapter C28, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

² Intellectual Property and Fashion in Nigeria'

<https://abo-law.com/intellectual-property-and-fashion-in-nigeria-how-can-fashion-designers-protect-their-creative-works/> accessed 19 March 2021

The copyright Act protects just the design on the surface that is, the law protects any artistic expression however this is limited to the expression and not the functionality of the design -which in fashion is crucial³. As a result, protection under the Nigerian Copyright Act is not available where a designer intends to mass produce his or her garments. This is a disadvantage to Nigerian designers because commercially marketed designs are unprotected under the Copyright Act.

This is totally not justified, because fashion design just like every other creative work from arts to architecture is a product of devoting time, energy and sufficient research. This in itself is against the theories on the need for intellectual property protection

After devoting considerable time and effort into creating custom designs, a designer presents his or her line of clothing, hand bags, eyewear and other accessories without the protection of intellectual property law. As a result, copy houses are able to knock off these designs and sell them at affordable prices, effectively stealing profits from the original designer. Such design piracy not only harms the designer financially, but also results in brand dilution and injury to the designers reputation⁴

Many foreign countries treat fashion design as an art form and thus, provide copyright protection to fashion designs. Under the French copyright law, fashion designs are given automatic protection on the date of creation, regardless of registration.⁵ Italian copyright law also recognizes fashion as a form of art, requiring the design to “have creative character or inherent artistic character”⁶

Therefore, the current forms of IP protection available are very limited in their fashion design applicability and an adequate form of protection is needed for American fashion designs.

2. INDUSTRIAL DESIGN AND PATENT

³‘The Place of the Law in the Nigerian Fashion Industry’
[https://africafashionlaw.com.ng/the-place-of-the-law-in-the-nigerian-fashion-industry-with-kike-
ojewale/](https://africafashionlaw.com.ng/the-place-of-the-law-in-the-nigerian-fashion-industry-with-kike-ojewale/) Accessed 19 March 2021

⁴ Ibid

⁵ French Copyright Act of 1783, Art.112-2

⁶ Brittany West; The new look for the fashion industry ; Redesigning copyright law with the innovative Design protection and piracy protection Act
<https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/jbel/vol5/iss1/3/> Accessed 20 March 2021

Another way fashion design receives protection is through the provisions of the Patent and Design Act. An industrial design is an intellectual property right governed by the Nigerian Patents and Designs Act. Under the Patents and Designs Act, Section 12 of the Act provides that, *“Any combination of lines or colours or both, and any three-dimensional form, whether or not associated with colours, is an industrial design, if it is intended by the creator to be used as a model or pattern to be multiplied by industrial process and is not intended solely to obtain a technical result”*⁷

The idea behind registering a design is to prevent others from reproducing the external design of the product. The owner of a registered design can prevent others from reproducing, importing, illicitly profiting, selling or utilizing it for commercial purposes.

Industrial design protects the aesthetic value and is very relevant to the fashion and textile design industry. A registered design is protected for a period of 5 years from the date of the application for registration. Protection may be renewed for two further consecutive periods of 5 years.⁸

The idea behind registering a design is to prevent Fashion Piracy such as counterfeiting and knock offs. ⁹While a knock-off is a close copy of the original fashion mimicking its design elements but sold under a different label; a counterfeit is a copy of the original fashion design as well as the brand logo or label of that design. In other words, counterfeit apparel is sold in an attempt to pass off as the original product. Counterfeit may also involve piracy in fashion design besides piracy in the logo or label of the fashion brand.¹⁰

In order to register a design in Nigeria under Nigeria’s Patents and Design Act: “Any anticipation of the design anywhere in the world, by any means whatsoever before the date of the application for registration of the relevant priority date destroys novelty.” ¹¹The applicant must

⁷ Patents and Designs Act (Chapter 344, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990).

⁸ Section 20 of the Patents and Designs Act

⁹ ‘Needless Stitches Understanding the Nigerian Intellectual Property Rights and Fashion’ www.mondaq.com/nigeria/trademark/940912/needles-stitches-understanding-the-nigerian-intellectual-property-rights-and-fashion-law- accessed 20 March 2021

¹⁰‘Needless Stitches Understanding the Nigerian Intellectual Property Rights and Fashion’ www.mondaq.com/nigeria/trademark/940912/needles-stitches-understanding-the-nigerian-intellectual-property-rights-and-fashion-law- accessed 20 March 2021

¹¹ Enyinna S. Nwauche, *Prior Use and Registration of Designs in Nigeria*, at 827.

consider whether or not the design is new and the applicant must not publicize the design before seeking to register the design. The requirements that the design needs to be novel and must not have been released can be a disadvantage to the designer who will be unable to ascertain the kind of reception the design will be given by the public before going through the effort of registering the design.

Also, Nigerian designers may seek protection by obtaining a design patent, which permits mass production, but is also difficult to secure. Design law aims to fill in the gaps where copyright falls short. However, the requirements which need to be fulfilled for any design to attract this form of protection are a little unrealistic. A design needs to be novel and it must not have been released to the public to attract design protection. A designer could be taking a risk as he or she could be unsure of how well such a design will be received by the public and so it will be difficult determining if the design would be worth protecting or not.¹²

Designers who chose this route are often impeded by the lengthy processing time required to obtain the patent, this is an inefficient form of fashion design protection considering the quick turnover rate of fashion design apparel. The fees associated with the application and registration process, and the burden to prove that their designs are entirely "new," vary significantly from each prior design in every country across the world. patents are available "only for designs that are truly 'new' and do not extend to designs that are merely re-workings of previously existing designs."¹³

The heightened originality requirement for a Patent design makes it difficult for the majority of fashion designs to qualify for the protection and considering the fact that most designs are oftentimes a reworking of the trends.

Fashion tends to change every season and a design that was once fashionable may not be fashionable two years later. This makes design patents unappealing to many fashion designers because by the time they receive protection for their designs, if such protection is granted, their designs may no longer be in style.

¹²'The Place of the Law in the Nigerian Fashion Industry'
[https://africafashionlaw.com.ng/the-place-of-the-law-in-the-nigerian-fashion-industry-with-kike-
ojewale/](https://africafashionlaw.com.ng/the-place-of-the-law-in-the-nigerian-fashion-industry-with-kike-ojewale/) accessed 20 March 2021

¹³ Alissandra Barrack 'is fashion art that should be protected?' Accessed 20 March 2021

The substantial time and money necessary to acquire a patent make patents an unappealing means of fashion design protection. Thus, making this protection not a feasible option for many fashion designers.

3. TRADEMARK

An alternative protection is covered by the Trademark Act. Trademark provides protection of a designer's mark, which serves as a source identifier. Although fashion designs cannot themselves be trademarked, trademarks can provide fashion design protection by incorporating the mark into the design itself.¹⁴

A trademark is a recognizable name or design, which is legally registered and used to identify and distinguish a product or entity from others. In order to register a trademark, a name or symbol must be able to identify and distinguish a product from other goods. Clothing lines and fashion designers can protect their brands, names, slogans, and logos. Once registered, it enables the trademark owner to take legal action against anyone who uses, sells or licenses the registered mark without permission. However, only the mark is as a matter of course protected and not the entire garment or accessory¹⁵. Unlike copyright and patent rights, trademark rights do not last for a fixed duration. Trademark rights can potentially last indefinitely as long as the owner continues to use the mark to identify its goods or services, and police unauthorized uses of its mark so that it continues to identify a single source in the market and not become generic.

Despite the sheer importance of IP in the fashion industry and beyond, it is a commonly misunderstood body of law, and its various elements are often used interchangeably when they are, in fact, distinct. Generally, trademarks do not protect the goods themselves, but rather serve

¹⁴ Chidera Anyawu ,An Uphill Battle Protecting Fashion Designs In Nigeria and Abroad <https://www.intellectualpropertylawblog.com/archives/protecting-fashion-designs-nigeria> accessed on 21 March 2021

¹⁵‘How can Fashion Designers protect Their Creative Work’ <https://abo-law.com/intellectual-property-and-fashion-in-nigeria-how-can-fashion-designers-protect-their-creative-works/> Accessed 20 March 2021

to protect the brand, preventing individuals from outright counterfeiting –passing off as other brands]¹⁶

One way that fashion designs may be protected is through trademarks. Trademark provides protection of a designer's mark, which serves as a source identifier.¹⁷ Although fashion designs cannot themselves be trademarked, trademarks can provide fashion design protection by incorporating the mark into the design itself,¹⁸ Such that, if an individual were to copy the design with the mark, they would be subject to trademark infringement.

Although some designers use this method to protect their designs, the vast majority of fashion designers are unable to protect their designs through trademarks because they do not necessarily include the mark within all designs.

First, trademark protection favors brands that have strong logos. Examples of strong logos include Louis Vuitton with its LV logo" or Chanel and its interlocking Cs. Trademarks help successful high-end brands create a luxurious brand image-protecting them from design copying because the item's appeal comes from the brand itself rather than the design. This also causes a disincentive in copying because the item loses its appeal without the logo.¹⁹ Brand strength ensures that there will always be consumers seeking the original design, despite the presence of counterfeits. ²⁰For example, there are many consumers that seek the original Burberry trademarked print despite the availability of affordable counterfeit versions in the market. Unfortunately, most fashion designers do not have this sort of consumer loyalty.

Most Nigerian fashion designers are not world-renowned designers and thus, do not have the luxurious brand appeal that such well-known designers possess. In Nigeria, designers do not impute logos on the fabric designs from *Sisiano* to *deola sagoe*, *Clan* and *LDA* to mention but a few, their design appeal is more from design functionality rather than the surface look or logo.

¹⁶ Brittany West; The new look for the fashion industry ; Redesigning copyright law with the innovative Design protection and piracy protection Act
<https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/jbel/vol5/iss1/3/> Accessed 20 March 2021

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Jasmine Martinez ; intellectual property right & fashion Design; An expansion of copyright Protection.

https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?public=true&handle=hein.journals/usflr53&div=17&start_page=369&collection=journals&set_as_cursor=8&men_tab=srchresults accessed 20 March 2021

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Ibid.

Moreover, with the exception of the high-end brands previously mentioned, the majority of fashion apparel does not have a visible logo. A large number of fashion apparel brands have the trademark located on the tag, which tends to be inside the garment, or on small portions of the clothing such as buttons.²¹Such designs can be easily copied with the absence of the logo remaining unnoticed. Therefore, for the vast majority of fashion designs, trademarks do not provide any practical protection against copying. Trademark only speaks of the creator rather than the functionality of the design. It is possible not to breach the trademark rights but still pirate the design.

Argument against Extending IP Protection to Fashion Design

Fashion design protection has been a controversial issue, with proponents on one side arguing for increased protections while others argue that increased protections will harm the fashion design industry. Despite the many indicators of a need for design protection, some proponents argue that fashion is a unique good that, unlike other items of creativity, strives without formal IP rights. Here, this comment considers the arguments made against fashion design IP rights.

A. The Piracy Paradox

One of the leading arguments against protecting fashion design is the argument that piracy in fashion design increases innovation. The leading proponents of this view are law professors Kal Raustiala and Christopher Sprigman. They argue that low IP protection for fashion design may paradoxically serve the fashion industry's interests better than high IP protection. Raustiala and Sprigman base their position on the quickly changing fashion cycle, arguing that as a design is copied by others and used in less expensive derivative works, it becomes more widely purchased. This drives status seekers to new designs in an effort to distinguish their style from the masses.²²They refer to this process as "induced obsolescence" where unregulated copying of fashion designs leads designs to become outdated much sooner than they would be if copying were prohibited.²³In turn, they argue that this pushes designers to come up with designs much sooner than they would otherwise and thus, increases innovation.²⁴ They also argue that piracy

²¹ Ibid.

²² West, *Supra* at 6

²³ Id.

²⁴ Kal Raustiala & Christopher Sprigman 'The Piracy Paradox Revisited' https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?public=true&handle=hein.journals/valr92&div=58&start_page=1687&collection=journals&set_as_cursor=0&men_tab=srchresults accessed 20 March 2021

paradoxically benefits the designers themselves because as designers increase the amount of designs they create they inevitably increase their sales.²⁵ However, this is an outdated view. As this comment will later explain, the process of copying designs has changed and advanced drastically throughout recent years, leading to substantial harms to innovation. Moreover, Raustiala and Sprigman fail to distinguish between copies that are a reworking of original designs and identical copies, arguing that copying in general promotes innovation.²⁶ However, it is important to distinguish close copying from interpretation and homage. The former harms innovation while the latter promotes²⁷

B. Protection of Fashion Design Would Decrease Innovation

Aside from the piracy paradox, other arguments are made against IP protection for fashion design, which claim that extending copyright protection would lead to a decrease in innovation. Some argue that most fashion design is a derivative work of past or current designs and not completely an original work. The argument made is that most having fashion design is a type of derivative work; therefore, providing copyright protection for such works would grant the copyright owner's exclusive rights to make copies of the original and all derivative works.²⁸ This would essentially give the copyright owner a monopoly over certain designs and force other designers to pay royalties in order to create derivative works. This could decrease innovation **by** designers who do not have the financial means to pay such royalties.

Further, it is argued that many designers engage in copying and while they may have an original design one season, the next season they will likely be copying a trend started **by** another designer, so it is in the fashion industry's best interest to allow copying.²⁹ This comment agrees with this argument, in that providing the current rights accorded **by** copyright protection to fashion design would provide too much design protection to the point that it limits innovation. However, this comment will later discuss this issue and instead propose a focus on a limited form of copyright protection for fashion design that will not impede innovation.

c. Increased Protections Would Harm Consumers

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Martinez ,Supra at 6

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Ibid

²⁹ Ibid.

One of the lesser arguments made against extending copyright protection to fashion design, which coincides with the previously stated argument, is that extending copyright protection could harm consumers. Take, for example, the High-end designer Chanel-if copyright protection were to extend to Chanel's fashion designs, Chanel would be able to become the exclusive supplier of its original designs.³⁰The vast majority of consumers cannot afford such high-priced items and, without the possibility of being able to buy cheap counterfeit versions of high-end designs, a large group of consumers would be excluded From participating in certain parts of the fashion industry. However, as previously stated, this comment considers the value of derivative works and this potential harm to consumers is of no concern. Moreover, it has been argued that this view is flawed because fashion is available at all price levels and consumers can obtain affordable designs "through the mass-market lines of influential designers.³¹[and] diffusion lines of high-end designer brands."³² Thus, it is not necessary for consumers to have counterfeit versions of a design available when they can purchase original designs from the more affordable lines of high-end designers.

E. Arguments in Favor of a Stronger Fashion Design Protection

The most compelling reason why stronger protection is required for fashion law is that the main goal of IP protection is to foster innovation, and only by granting exclusive rights to those who invest their time, money, and effort into innovating will we ensure that they continue to do

So If piracy continues to be difficult to punish, those who create original fashion designs will make less profit because consumers will most likely buy the less-expensive option, and designers will not be incentivized to continue creating original designs or even enter the market at all.³³

In addition, the current IP equilibrium system is focused on status and luxury rather than fostering innovation, as evidenced in this Note. Stronger protection for fashion designers would likely lead to designers taking bigger risks and innovating more, instead of the usual luxury brands using already existing models and including their strong trademarks on them to prevent others from copying their designs.

³⁰ Id.

³¹ Id

³² Id.

³³ West. Supra 6

The "piracy-paradox" argument does not distinguish between "close copies" and "trends," but this distinction is very important in the fashion industry, because only close copies are devastating to the market, whereas trends do not have such a detrimental effect.³⁴ Proponents of a more stringent fashion design protection believe that stronger protection should be granted only against "close copying." Trends do not deter consumers from buying the original design instead of copies, because they can still distinguish between the two items, whereas "close copies" decrease the attractiveness of buying the (usually) more expensive original over the cheap copy.³⁵

Another reason supporting the conclusion that fashion designs should be subject to stronger protection is that there is no logical reason as to why other original creations, such as books, paintings, movies, and works of architecture receive strong protection, whereas fashion designs are completely ignored by the current legal system.³⁶ The required skills necessary to create fashion designs and products are comparable to those necessary to create any work of "fine art," and therefore there is no valid reason to deny them a similar protection.³⁷ Finally, it has been demonstrated that conferring stronger IP protection to fashion designs would help the industry grow, which in the long term would benefit society as a whole.

THE NEED FOR AN IP PROTECTION IN THE FASHION INDUSTRY;

The emergence of digital technology on the technological landscape has impacted the delicate copyright balance in a variety of ways. The introduction of social media created a new world for advertising and distribution and has played a role in the rapid rising and falling in popularity of many brands. Social media has also helped foster co-branding and endorsement opportunities between fashion brands and celebrities or other social media personalities, which has the benefit of allowing all parties to draw from larger public audiences. These new developments in advertising and media strategy have led to the emergence of new legal intricacies that have helped develop "fashion law" into its niche practice area. Thus, leading Fashion labels and brands to become more protective of their intellectual property rights.

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Denisse Garcia Fashion 2.0 IT's time for the fashion industry to get better , custom-tailored legal protection
https://heinonline.org/HOL/Page?public=true&handle=hein.journals/drexell11&div=9&start_page=337&collection=journals&set_as_cursor=12&men_tab=srchresults Accessed 20 March 2021

³⁶ Ibid

³⁷ Ibid

Nigerian intellectual property scholars have recognized these dilemmas facing Nigerian fashion designers in light of Nigeria's ascension in the world fashion marketplace and suggested intellectual property reform to remedy them. In an interview with *The Guardian*, Professor Adebambo Anthony Adewopo, an intellectual property law scholar at Lagos State University and Senior Advocate of Nigeria stated, "[Nigerian intellectual property] laws have remained largely unsuited to the emergent commercial and technological development" and "[w]hat [Nigeria] need[s] is a holistic reform of IP in substance and in form, including a well-articulated national IP and innovation policy."³⁸

Recommendations

1. PROPOSED THE FASHION DESIGN PROTECTION AND PIRACY PROHIBITION ACT

One approach to design protection in fashion is to create a purpose-made statutory right.

Defining what a design is giving a new definition to what is original/new as it relates to the fashion industry' It could contain;

Redefining Originality;

A design is "original" if it is the result of the designer's creative endeavor that provides a distinguishable variation over prior work pertaining to similar articles which is more than merely trivial and has not been copied from another source' In the case of a fashion design, a design shall not be deemed to have been copied from a protected design if it is original and not closely and substantially similar in overall visual appearance to a protected design.¹³⁹

Duration of Protection;

Under the Proposed bill, fashion designs would receive protection for three years.

³⁸ Betram Nwannekanma, *'Nigeria's intellectual property laws not suited for emerging commercial and technological development'*, Oct. 3, 2017, available at <https://guardian.ng/features/law/nigerias-intellectual-property-laws-not-suited-for-emerging-commercial-and-technological-development/>. Accessed 21 March 2021

³⁹ West, *supra* at 6

Registration would be required to secure protection, and would have to take place within three months of the public disclosure of the design. The bill would prohibit copying both the protected design as well as images of the design.

2. Compulsory licensing

IP already has accommodated the interests of creators and copyists in one area: the compulsory licensing of musical compositions.⁴⁰ The statute permits anyone who wishes to use a musical work copyrighted by its author to do so, and requires the author to permit the use, in return for payment of a set license fee and acknowledgement of the creator's authorship. This could be adopted for the fashion industry and could address two of the critical issues in the fashion design context. First, the design creator receives some compensation. Secondly, the design creator's authorship is acknowledged because the copyist would be obliged to disclose the fact of the copying.

Adoption of this to the Nigerian Market will help put structure in place in the fashion industry if *ABA* Boys are able to get licensed from already established Nigerian Brands they can work hand in hand to produce these Apparels or fashion items that can bring about economic boost and recovery. The problem with the *ABA* industry is not like they do not produce good things but do not have a face, they lack accessibility and recognition. Basically, they are not rated. Partnering with an already established fashion brand like Orange culture, Trax Apparel that have international recognition and brand credibility will help them overcome their flaws thereby reducing piracy.

3. Arbitration panel to be set up for determining design issues

Just like the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) Arbitration panel set up to look into dispute bothering on Domain names, an Arbitration panel will be set up to look into disputes on design ownership, protection and infringement.

Here the supervisory body will create a framework of procedural rules that states the following;

(a) An expedited arbitral procedure based on submission of the design items at issue;

⁴⁰ Ibid

(b) To a panel appointed by one of a number of industry or arbitral convening authorities, with specified qualifications. Disputants could agree on which convening organization would hear the dispute.

4. Copyright protection should be extended to fashion design to prevent inconsistent application of copyright law.
5. Copyright laws could be reformed to allow for full protection without the limitation of production.
6. Furthermore, structures should be established to ensure a less tedious registration process; for example, most applications at the Registry are still completed manually as opposed to electronically.

VI. CONCLUSION:

Even though Nigeria has never had formal IP protection for fashion design, in a modern world of almost instantaneous piracy, no concrete reasons exist to prevent adoption of such a protection policy now. The advent of technology makes protection of fashion design more important than ever before. Fashion design should receive the protection it deserves. The IP theory of copyright protection justifies protection for fashion designs.

Extending copyright protection to fashion will not curtail innovation, but rather will spur innovation by encouraging those retailers and wholesalers currently involved in copying to create new designs. Furthermore, trends in fashion will not be affected by the protection of IP because the bill will protect only those custom designs within a trend.

Application of standard copyright law to fashion designs will likely not be successful. However, some degree of protection is necessary to protect the work of designers and to be a sufficient compromise between balancing the need to protect the creative expression of ideas with the difficulty of regulation and practicality of protection.

Although high IP protection is not guaranteed to help the Nigerian fashion industry, discouraging piracy and protecting designers seems a better policy than not doing so. Continued refusal to allow copyright protection of fashion designs seems to suggest that fashion design is not an art that deserves IP protection.

Current intellectual protection laws are ill-suited to protect fashion design and Nigeria needs an urgent rejig of its laws to suit the growing demand of the fashion industry.